

Product Sound Design and Application: Overview

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Abstract

Designing sounds for products is a relatively new concept that still lacks a systematic procedure. Formerly, a pleasing sound would be realized by, e.g., decreasing the sound pressure level. The sound of a vacuum cleaner would be changed if it sounded unpleasantly loud. Nowadays it is acknowledged that product sound design should be integrated in the main design process to enhance the user experience both on ergonomic and hedonic levels. For example, the sound producing parts of an expensive car (i.e., engine, doors, gearbox, cabin auditory warnings, etc.) are designed to reflect the main requirements for the car design such as reliability, comfort, safety, luxury, and consequently a pleasant drive. However, an integration of the sound design into the design process of a product requires specific tools and methods. This paper addresses this issue and presents two methods and a tool by which designers can model and demonstrate their conceptual ideas for the sound of the product under development.

Keywords: product sound, design, tool, methodology, communication, sketch, model

Need for Product Sound Design

Alberto Alessi stated in a recent interview on Euronews (Le Mag, 21 April 2006) that when buying products users do not seek functionality anymore—nowadays functionality is taken for granted in any mass-produced product—they rather seek experience, fun, pleasure, and comfort while using a product. This view corresponds to Desmet's (2002) basic model of product emotions which suggests that users may have various concerns with respect to the product use and these concerns may evoke emotional responses. One of these concerns might be related to the sound property of the product which has indeed the potential to influence users' behavior and appreciation of products.

Sounds' influence on users may directly stem from the spectral-temporal composition of the sound itself (Västfjäll et al., 2002) or it may also stem from concurrent cognitive judgments both on the sound and its relation to its source (i.e., the product) and from the meaning derived from this relationship (Özcan & van Egmond, 2005). An example of the spectral-temporal influence would be the sound of a vacuum cleaner. This sound may evoke negative emotional responses on a user due to its high-pitch and loudness level. An example of the cognitive influence would be the sound of a coffee maker. Despite its noisiness and sharpness in the spectral composition, this sound may evoke positive emotional responses on a user due to anticipation of a relaxed time while drinking coffee. Some studies have already shown the emotional effects of product sounds on users (Västfjäll, 2002; Västfjäll et al., 2002; Västfjäll et al., 2003). For domestic appliance sounds, emotional responses often lay on the negative side of the emotion spectrum (Özcan & van Egmond, 2005) which already creates new avenues for product sound related research and design.

In marketing, a product's visual property is the most important aspect for the first-moment-of-truth (i.e., shelf-presence of products) to convince the potential user to choose between the two similar products from different brands. However, users' satisfaction with products depends highly on the properties of the product that are available only in the second-moment-of-truth (i.e., product use). Sound as a property naturally emerges only when the product is functioning. In the course of the product usage, users experience whether or not the produced sound is fitting the

total design and the function of the product (Blauert and Jekosch, 1997). So, a sound's inappropriateness to the product may cause user dissatisfaction. Therefore, not to have any unconsidered effects, product sound should be designed to fit the product values.

Product Sounds

We define product sounds as the sounds that are emitted by products as a result of their functionality. For example, a vacuum cleaner makes sound because of the running engine, rotating fan, and air-flow in the tubes. As the name 'product' embodies various artifacts that are mass-produced and entered in the consumer market, product types may vary in the domains of packaging, personal care products, food, and domestic appliances. Relevant to us is the domain of domestic appliances. In this domain, we have defined six perceptually relevant product sound categories (Özcan, van Egmond, and Jacobs, submitted, 2006). These categories are air, alarm, cyclic, impact, liquid, and mechanical sounds. People react differently to the sounds in these categories and their concerns vary from one category to another. For alarm sounds the derived meaning (e.g., 'food is ready' for the alarm of the microwave oven) is important to a user, for mechanical sounds the type of source becomes important.

Product Design

The main lack in product sound design is a systematic methodology that organizes the sound related design activity. Sound designers also lack tools that assist them create new ideas and communicate about the sound of the product in development. However, methods from product design can be applied to product sound design. So, in order to fill these gaps, we analyzed existing methods for product design in terms of product development processes and design communication. Figure 1 organizes the relationship between the product development process and the activities that designers perform in order to communicate with the design team. In the figure, designers' activities are organized according to the design phases where they mainly occur. Here, the outputs of these activities are also mentioned as 'communication methods'. Figure 1 also summarizes the ideas gathered in this section. Thus, this section will focus on the

basic steps of product development processes and later discuss the methods of design communication in relation to the figure.

Product Development Processes

Designing is considered as a practical problem-solving activity. According to Roozenburg and Eekels' cycle of design-problem-solving (1995), a solution (i.e., decision about the design) is obtained in five main steps: analysis, synthesis, simulation, evaluation, and decision. This cycle is followed in each and every step of the design processes. That means in each step of the design process, the problems of that stage is analyzed; ideas that form the preliminary solutions are synthesized; suitable solutions are expressed in forms of simulation; the output of the simulation is evaluated; and finally upon the results of the evaluation it is decided on the most optimal solution.

Other methodologies describing the design process (French, 1985; Pahl & Beitz, 1986; VDI 2221, 1987) consist of four main phases (see Figure 1): analysis of the problem, conceptual design, embodiment design, and detailing (see, Cross, 2000 for the detailed comparisons of these design processes):

- *Analysis of the problem.* The nature of the design problem is ill-defined. That is, there is no one definitive formulation of the problem, any problem formulation may embody inconsistencies, formulations of the problem are solution dependent, proposing solutions is a means of understanding the problem, and there is no definitive solution to the problem (Cross, 2000).
- *Conceptual design.* Ideas are generated and assessed in the conceptual design phase. Perhaps, this is the most demanding and mentally exhaustive phase of the design process, because designers consider all aesthetics, ergonomics, emotion, production, and cost related aspects of the product in question and make a synthesis out of them. This is a creative phase in which overall function and important sub-functions of the product are determined. As a result, several possible design solutions are generated as concepts. The outcome of this phase has an influential power on the total design of the product. One of the most agreeable concepts is taken further.

- *Embodiment design.* In the next phase (embodiment design), the concept is embodied as the preliminary design of the product and functioning features of the product are defined. This is the phase in which iterations take place in order to refine the design based on technical and economic considerations. The outcome is often drawings of a functioning product on paper and a list of product parts.
- *Detailing.* The definitive design should be detailed in order to safely communicate with the manufacturers and distributors. All technical specifications are done in this phase including materials and parts to be used, dimensions, geometrical shape, etc. The outcome is ‘product documents’ that encloses technical drawings and instructions for the production assembly, testing, and transport.

These phases described above are not rigidly separated. Overlaps may occur especially between conceptual design and embodiment design phases. Because the goal is not clearly defined in a design problem, the path to solve a design problem—and achieve an optimal solution—happens to be flexible with iterative explorations in each phase of the design process. So, the whole design process can be fed by any alternative solutions at any point in the process—this is especially so if one sees the whole design process as a practical problem solving mechanism.

Design Communication

Product design is conducted by several teams of different disciplines. The design teams simultaneously generate ideas and evaluate them in order to achieve the specified goal. The members of the teams should have a common ground on the design decisions and evaluations. So, the ideas for solutions should be translated equally especially from discipline to discipline. Thus, communication between the design teams becomes an essential factor in the course a design process. Well-expressed ideas lead to efficient communication. Efficient communication among the design team speeds up the design process and therefore decreases the cost.

Figure 1. Design process, designers' communication related activities, and communication methods.

Design communication can be carried out efficiently by the outputs of the *simulation* step in the problem solving cycle. One of the challenges in design communication is to summarize one's ideas and present them to others who might be unfamiliar with the terminology used or the methods applied. To facilitate this, designers perform several activities and use several methods to develop their ideas and communicate them with the design team (see Figure 1). Some of these activities and methods presented in Figure 1 intend to (i) visualize the ideas (sketches, drawings), (ii) imitate the product-to-be-built (mock-ups, clay modeling, 3D digital models, physical models). (iii) present in text the company—or design—values (reports, tables), (iv) verbalize the solution-related concerns (discussions, conversations), (v) facilitate production (technical

drawings), and (*vi*) instruct assembly and use (manuals). These methods of expressions vary in the degree of details depending on the design phase in which they are used (mock-ups might be used in the conceptual design phase, 3D digital models might be used in the embodiment phase, and prototypes might be used in detailing phase).

Modeling is a very commonly used tool in design communication. Roozenburg & Eekels (1995) discern four main categories of models based on the similarity between the original product and the model: structure, iconic, analogue, and mathematical models. Relevant for sound design are structure and iconic models. *Structure* models can provide a quick first impression of the appearance, functioning, and manufacturing possibilities, and they are often a source of ideas (*p.* 243). The main aim of this type of modeling is the visualization of the qualitative structure of an object. Some examples are sketches, dummies, flow diagrams, etc. *Iconic* models simulate solutions in greater details than structure models. By giving a 3-dimensional overview, they represent the function and the properties (e.g., geometric, thermal, dynamic, etc.) of the original object. Mock-ups, scale models, and prototypes are some of the examples.

Sketching and verbalization are commonly used tools for thinking, reasoning, creating, and discussing. Through *sketching*, ideas are generated and possibilities of product use or functionality are explored. Ferguson (1992) discerns three types of sketching: ‘thinking’ sketches, ‘talking’ sketches, and ‘prescriptive’ sketches. ‘Thinking’ sketches aid a designer to explore his/her ideas and visualize them. ‘Talking’ sketches aid a group of designers to explain their ideas and discuss them. ‘Prescriptive’ sketches aid a designer to communicate to multidisciplinary design team. For visual design problems sketching is a powerful tool that aids the visual thinking and expression. By *verbalizing* their ideas, designers convey their concerns and suggestions. In a design team, engineers seem to express themselves well in a verbal conversation; they tend to model their ideas with words (Lloyd et al., 2001)—which creates high cognitive load on the engineers’ verbal communication skills—, whereas industrial designers seem to make use of graphical representations to express their ideas. Relying on mere verbal communication may have its own drawbacks. Words may become insufficient to describe, e.g., perceived qualities of the material chosen for a product. The ambiguity in the verbal conversation can be cancelled by, e.g., visualization of an object. Moreover, designing has become an

international activity due to cost effectiveness and knowledge share. It is common to see that different design processes are held in different countries. This brings out its own problems because terminologies used in one country might not match in another (Martens & Giragama, 2002).

To our knowledge, the above described methods of modeling and communication do not make use of the auditory property of the object-in-design. It is our aim to include ‘auditory’ models in design communication.

Product Sound Design

Its Short History

For a long time sounds emitted by products have been regarded as noise and therefore as an undesired product feature that should be reduced or eliminated. Noise-control methods have been used to design noise enclosures, isolation systems, and silencers to make the products more acceptable. The main problem with the noise was its loudness. Sound quality control would entail the sound level measurement and comparison of the measurement with the target sound level. For example, when a vacuum cleaner sounded as loud as 78 dB, engineers would design new parts to dampen and isolate the noise which reduced the sound level to, e.g., 70 dB. Because such a method disallows designers to foresee the upcoming problems related to sound, noise-control becomes an independent design process. This results in additional cost due to the extra materials used and man-hours spent. Manufacturers often disfavored noise control because of its costly nature. Noise control methods have not been abandoned—yet there are some application areas for them fitting certain design requirements (Bodden et al., 2002). However, recently design teams started to incorporate sound in their design decisions rather than solving the problem when it occurs.

In the recent view, product design teams consider sound as one of the inherit features of the sheer product functionality (other product features would be form geometry, material texture, size, weight, etc.). Designers should consider sound as a challenging problem to be solved in the design process and abandon the opinion that sound is as a negative product feature which must be

cancelled promptly (Lyon, 2000). Thus, designers should seek ways to explore how to exploit sound to enhance the user experience with products.

Product Sound Design - Now

Sound design is mostly practiced during detailing of the product design process. In the detailing, prototypes are built and trial runs are conducted to simulate the functionality of the original product with the real parts. A functioning prototype naturally creates sound, which is indicative of product's inherent sound. So, this is the phase where the sound quality of the product can be assessed. If the results of the assessment fail to reveal any good correlation to the design requirements of the product, then the sound design needs to be conducted. The parts that fail to produce the desired sound are changed and replaced with another one, and then the sound quality of the product is re-assessed. This iterative process continues until the desired sound is created.

In some cases, concepts and alternatives are created for a sound design. This is done by recording the sound of the prototype and modifying it with the help of a computer. Such a modification is done in a way that it represents the sound of the part that should be replaced with the problematic part. In this stage, suggestions are given with respect to the product parts to be used. After having a few alternatives and the original sound of the prototype, the sound quality assessments can be done on the digital sound files of the suggestions. The modified sound can also be used as a communication tool for the design team to discuss how to proceed further. The most preferred sound is taken further with the requirements for the new prototype to be built.

Product Sound Quality

Physical character of a sound has psychological correlates (Solomon, 1958; von Bismarck, 1974; Björk, 1985). Similarly, a product sound—depending on its spectral-temporal structure—conveys high-level hedonic attributes rather than evoking only sensory perception/(un)pleasantness. Lageat et al. (2003) links the 'concrete' attributes of product sounds (i.e., spectral-temporal properties.) to the product's hedonic attributes (i.e., pleasant, aggressive, discreet, luxury) suggesting that one can manipulate the 'concrete' characteristics of a sound in order to convey hedonic attributes of product through sound. In especially automotive industry, this is a rather exploited area. For example, car manufacturer DaimlerChrysler investigated the degree to which

sportiness and sophistication of a car could be represented by the loudness, timbre, and roughness of its engine sound (Letens, 2000). Door sounds of expensive cars are also designed to convey luxury, comfort, and safety.

Similar approaches have been widely studied under the name of product sound quality assessment. Sound quality assessment suggests the adequacy of the sound to the product it belongs to (Blauert & Jekosch, 1997). In other words, the sound should convey the same values as the product. In a framework, Blauert & Jekosch (1997) discuss the process by which users assess product sounds. In this process, assessment of a sound is done upon auditory perception, and this judgment is continuously fed by cognitive and emotional processes, and by the input from other sensory modalities. This framework also suggests that mere psychophysical measurement of a sound (e.g., sound pressure level or sharpness) does not suffice for determining its psychological effects on users. Other similar approach was posed later by Fog & Pedersen (1999) who point out to the subjectivity of the sound quality measures and unexpectancy of the judgments. In their model user judgments pass through two filters: (a) users' sensory sensitivity and selectivity towards the product sound, and (b) users' 'background, expectations, interest, emotions, and mood'. Lyon's (2000) approach is similar to the one of Blauert & Jekosch's (1997). These models intend to map the sound's physical instrumental measure (absolute) to psychoacoustical attributes (objective), and that to user judgments (subjective).

Guski (1997) discusses the methods used to analyze product sound quality and indicates three psychologically relevant aspects: (a) stimulus-response compatibility (reaction time measurements), (b) pleasantness of sounds (questionnaires), and (c) identifiability of sounds (recognition—yes-no—tests and/or verbal descriptions). A questionnaire is the most frequently used method (see, Altinsoy et al., 1998; Lyon, 2000; Lageat et al., 2003) which tests whether the sound conveys the desired attributes of the product. The attributes may represent ergonomics, safety, emotions, hedonics, psychoacoustics, and other attributes depending on product's design. Another method is the analysis of the verbal descriptions. This method is commonly used in recognition test checking the identifiability of product sounds. Interpretations of the verbal descriptions are made to understand the underlying factors of the product sound quality (for a

general opinion on the vocabulary listeners use to describe product sounds, refer to Özcan & van Egmond, 2005).

The methods described above can be used either prior to designing sounds to determine the problems with the sound of an existing product or they can be used during prototyping phase of the product to see whether the desired values have been achieved.

Complexity of Designing Product Sounds

Designing sounds for products is a complex process. Below we explain the reasons that contribute to this complexity.

Sound as an indirect result of moving product parts. Because sound is a consequence of moving parts in a product, designing the sound would mean changing the physical properties of the moving parts such as shape, material, and size. When a product is being designed, parts and functionality are determined with respect to the design problem and its requirements for the solutions. It is the interaction of parts and the action involved in the functionality that cause the sound; so, sound design cannot be independent of these aspects. Thus, there should be a good compromise between the design of desired aspects of the product and of the sound.

Consequential outcome of the sound design. Sound design may cause a chain reaction in the design cycle. Hubka and Eder (1988) explain in a framework how design properties are linked to each other and to internal and external properties of production cycle. Adopting the framework, we can assume that changing a part in the product in order to design the sound may influence the allocated space in the product casing, which would influence the size and weight of the product, and which would affect the packaging design, distribution, and finally the cost of the product.

Physical absence of sound during the design process. In a design process, one cannot talk about the existence of sound during the problem analysis and conceptual design phase. Sound, as a product property, starts to emerge only when the first models of the product is built (embodiment design). Very often only the working prototypes emit sounds that may represent the original sound. Only in the embodiment phase designers consider including sound design in their design

conversations. This is not handy as our aim is to include sound design in the conceptual design phase.

Communication about the auditory properties of a product. It is not clear from the start of the design process what kind of sound stream a product will emit. Designers, therefore, have to rely on their imagination during design meetings to communicate about the psychological effects the sound will have on the users and to predict, in the absence of sound, what needs to be done in terms of sound design. In such cases, the potential product sound needs to be reproduced from memory by retrieving the a priori encoded sounds emitted by similar products or product parts. As the recalled sounds may not clearly represent the potential sound of the product, the judgments would be based on some information that might even be irrelevant to the actual design problem. This may cause misconceptions among the design teams that may lead time and resources loss. However, the early inclusion of the product sound in a design discussion would facilitate the design communication about sounds, and auditory judgments would benefit from it.

Proposed Solution

Sound design as a process should run parallel to the main product design process. Design teams should incorporate the sound related problems in their agenda already in the beginning of the product development process and invest effort in it in the subsequent phases. Doing this would prevent later occurring unexpected problems caused by sound. In Figure 2, suggestions for sound design related communication methods during a design process are proposed. This figure works similarly to Figure 1, moreover incorporates designers' sound design related activities and communication methods. Below, these methods are explained in more details following Figure 2.

In problem analysis phase, designers should include sound in their *discussions* and *auditorily exemplify* the sound related problem. The examples can be created by recording the sound of the products or by demonstrating the problem with the presence of the working product in question.

In conceptual design phase sketching is a common method to explore ideas and visualize them. So, our suggestion is creating *sounding sketches* for sound-related problems in order to

'audiolize' the product sound. Sounding sketches can be recordings of any object that has the potential to represent the sound desired. Or, these sketches can be collections of materials and objects that would exemplify the desired features of the product sound or the product itself. These sound examples might be ambiguous, so, they do not aim to represent the original sound, but they rather represent concepts.

In the embodiment design, the ideas are materialized and parts-to-be-used are determined. Then, models are produced that represent (and imitate) roughly how the product looks or function. So, our second suggestion is creating *sounding models* to simulate the original sound in greater details than sounding sketches. Sounding models can be the composition of sound producing parts. As a communication tool, sounding model summarizes designers' ideas about the proposed sound and makes it easy to discuss the suitability and the feasibility of the proposed solution. However, designers lack a tool to model the sound. Such a tool is under development within our research group and in the next section its functionalities will be briefly explained.

In the detailing phase, a prototype exists to test the functionality of the product. As the sound produced also represents the original sound of the product, sound quality assessments can be done using *questionnaires*. The results of which can be used to determine the final appropriateness of the sound to the product. The *sound of the prototype* can also be used as a reference for the original sound during production.

Figure 2. Proposed methods for product sound design related communication.

Tool for creating 'sounding models'

The main problem in simulating sound in the embodiment phase is the lack of sound. If sounds were available, designers would easily be able to create soundscapes (i.e., sound stream of functioning product) and compare the alternatives. Designers may always decompose products to separately record the sound of the parts they need. However, it would be time-consuming and unpractical. Therefore, we are developing a tool that compensates this lack and allows designers to simulate soundscapes.

Sound Library

This tool's main feature is the sound library. The library contains previously recorded sounds of product parts. Because the library may not contain all possible parts that exist in the manufacturer or that a designer desires to have, the tool allows designers to manipulate the previously recorded sound. Manipulation is based on changing the physical properties of a sound. By playing with certain parameters, a designer creates the desired sound.

Functionalities of the tool

The tool has three main functionalities that aid a designer to finalize a sound simulation (i.e., sounding model):

- *Assembly.* The tool allows designers to create a functioning product just by using sounds. By positioning the sounds on the timeline according to the order of event occurrence, the simulation is roughly finished.
- *Design.* As described earlier, by manipulating the individual sounds on the specific physical parameters, a designer creates the desired sound.
- *Evaluation.* The tool incorporates algorithms for parameters such as roughness, sharpness, loudness, tonality, and pitch are used to determine the acceptability of the sound on a sensory level.

The tool is very basic and its functionality is based on intuitive actions that allows a designer to explore his/her ideas. So, it can be used by any designer who is novice in designing product sounds. As a first step, we aim design students as prospect users for the tool. We believe that it is important to educate design students as being aware of this rapidly emerging need for product sound design.

Conclusions

Methods aim to help (novice) designers to choose tools suitable for the purpose of their design activity. Methods also guide designers how to use the selected tools, in what condition, and at what stage of the design process. Therefore, we believe that the product sound design related communication methods and the sound modeling tool presented in this paper support this view.

The proposed methods enable (sound) designers to systematically tackle the sound design process and to efficiently communicate the sound related design problems/solutions. Thus, the complexity of product sound design will be diminished to a certain extent.

Suggestions for Future

Before designing product sounds, the relation of the sound to the product it belongs to should be examined. Every product exhibits a different character. A proper sound design for one product does not necessarily correspond to a proper sound design of another. It is important to define the problems with product sounds in the context of human behavior, as users have the vote for the acceptability of the product. People exhibit certain behavioral patterns and action tendencies to any object they encounter around them (Plutchik, 1984; Frijda; 1986). Relevant to us is people's reactive behavior to objects. That is, people may **accept**, **reject**, or **ignore** an object depending on the context in which the object is available. When designing sounds, as a first step it is important to determine the psychological effects of the sound on people and their causes. For example, a standard digital alarm clock sound, which is highly present in an environment, can be found unpleasant. People may **reject** this sound due to the sound quality—high-pitched, sharp, loud, etc.—however, considering the function of the product they may **accept** it. Or in another example, a loud sound may be **rejected** for a city car because it causes noise-pollution, **accepted** for a sports car because it indicates power, or **ignored** for an old classic car because it only signifies old-fashioned technology. These behavioral concerns could form the guidelines for the type of sound to be designed.

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